

Sequential Oscillations with Entrainment Type Behaviour in Mixed Substrate BZ System

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Sequential oscillations in redox potential have been observed in BZ oscillating system on mixing solution A* containing acetone dicarboxylic acid with citric acid ethyl acetoacetate or acetylacetone. An entrainment type behaviour also occurred marked by a dominant high amplitude phase of oscillation at two different temperatures. These are attributed to large number of intermediates effective in triggering off the oscillations. A tentative mechanism based on FKN mechanism has been provided.

OSCILLATIONS have been reported^{1,2} in chemical systems when a binary mixture of two organic compounds is used as a substrate in cerium catalysed oxidation using acid bromate. In some cases¹ the role of reducer being played by one compound while the other responding readily to bromination. Chance *et al.*³ created the interest in biochemical oscillators by their work on the undamped sequential oscillations of NADH in yeast. This led to a search for similar behaviour in chemical homogenous systems. The glyoxalic acid-malonic acid mixture in BZ reaction studied by Koner and Epstein⁴ appears to show entrainment type behaviour where only oscillations due to glyoxalic acid were identified. Epstein *et al.*⁵ suggested sequential oscillations in binary combination of acetylacetone, malonic acid and ethyl acetoacetate. Besides the above views, hardly any example of mixed organic substrate exhibiting oscillations have so far been reported. In this communication, we report a very interesting type behaviour in which an unusually high amplitude phase of oscillations flanked by normal oscillations observed when acetonedicarboxylic acid $\text{Ac}(\text{COOH})_2$ in coordination with Ce^{III} contained in solution A* was mixed with citric acid (C.A.) or ethylacetoacetate (E.A.A.) or acetylacetone (Ac.Ac). Acetonedicarboxylic acid, however, has been reported^{6,7} as a single substrate in BZ reaction.

Experimental

All solutions were prepared in 1.5 M H_2SO_4 medium using AnalaR grade chemicals. A mixture of 1/180 M citric acid (10 ml) and 0.1 M Ce^{IV} sulphate (1.1 ml) allowed to stand for 2 h, was termed as solution-A*. This was mixed with a solution (10 ml) of the other component of binary organic substrate and 0.03 M KBrO_3 solution (10 ml). Oscillations were monitored⁶ by recording redox potential as a function of time using bright platinum

electrode coupled with reference calomel electrode in a Naina electronic digital recorder. All the investigations were made in a thermostat at two different temperatures 20 and 26°, while the solution was constantly stirred at 1000 r.p.m.

The presence of intermediate dibromoethylacetoacetate was confirmed by iodometric titrations of the ethereal extract of mixture. Formic acid was found by mercurimetric technique in all the mixtures (left for 2 days) in which all the oscillations had ceased. Free bromine was detected at several stages of reaction with the help of fluoroscein. A most conspicuous liquid end product of system involving Ac.Ac was confirmed to be diacetyl (b.p. 89°) extracted with chloroform and condensed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride to convert into dimethylglyoxime (a white powder, m.p. 234°).

Results and Discussions

Table 1 shows the results of mixing C.A., E.A.A. or Ac.Ac with solution A* at different temperatures while Fig. 1 is the typical trace of such systems depicting sequential oscillations with characteristic wave forms.

Fig. 1. Potential vs time curve for system of solution-A* mixed with 0.0056 M C.A. and 0.03 M KBrO_3 at $26 \pm 0.05^\circ$.

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For citric acid :

For ethyl acetoacetate :

The dihydroxy product (not identified) must be changing immediately to formic and acetic acids which were duly identified. Thus

The other product ethanol of reaction (vi) also not detected, is proposed to have oxidised into acetic acid in the prevailing conditions.

For acetyl acetone : Spectral studies¹¹ and our results of redox titration of acetyl acetone against Ce^{IV} indicate maximum consumption of oxidant equivalent to six electrons only which suggests the following stoichiometry,

The end-product diacetyl in this system, though supports the stoichiometry, the oxidation due to other intermediate species HOBr or BrO₂ oxidising acetylacetone via bromination can not be ruled out.

Thus it seems that by mixing substrates in appropriate amounts, several intermediates come into play, some of which were effective enough to promote periodic oscillations. Certain combinations of intermediates at a particular instant drove the system to oscillate with unusually high amplitude, followed by diminished amplitude when prominently effective intermediates had almost consumed. However, somewhat similar phenomenon of deterministic chaotic oscillations were suggested¹² very recently to be caused by the presence of large number of intermediates.

References

1. R. P. RASTOGI and K. D. S. YADAV, *Indian J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1977, **7**, 417; R. A. SCHMITZ, K. R. GRAZIANO and J. L. HUDSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1977, **67**, 3040; E. J. HEILWEL and J. R. EPSTEIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1979, **83**, 1359.
2. NOSZTICZIUS, *Mages. Kim. Foly.*, 1979, **85**, 330.
3. B. CHANCE, B. HESS and H. BETZ, *Biochem. Phys. Res. Commun.*, 1964, **16**, 182.
4. R. KONER and I. R. EPSTEIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 4073.
5. I. R. EPSTEIN, M. I. HENCHMAN and E. J. HEILWEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 3698.
6. H. C. MISHRA, A. N. OJHA and K. BHATHENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 725.
7. H. C. MISHRA, A. N. OJHA and K. BHATHENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 510.
8. H. C. MISHRA and C. M. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **54**, 857.
9. R. J. FIELD, E. KOROS and R. M. NOYES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 8649.
10. R. J. FIELD and R. M. NOYES, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1974, **60**, 1877.
11. S. M. TSIMBLER, L. L. SHEVCHENCO and V. K. GRIGOREVA, *Zh. Prikl. Spektrosk.*, 1969, **10**, 522.
12. J. SZAMOSI and S. J. LASKY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 1995; P. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 304.